

STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF TiO₂, WO₃, ZnO and SnO₂ FOR MODIFIED ZINC - TITANIUM DIOXIDE NANOCOMPOSITES SMART COATINGS

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ABSTRACT

The recent breakthrough in convectional materials has led to the emergence of novel and promising materials, which have found wide applications in today's technology. This study characterized the structure and optoelectronic properties of a modified Zn-TiO₂ nano-composite coating on mild steel. This was to develop smart coating materials for corrosion sensors in petrochemical industries. The smart coatings of the modified Zn-TiO₂ nano-composite coatings were electrolytically produced on mild steel from a zinc bath, with its co-deposition of nanoparticles of TiO₂, WO₃, ZnO and SnO₂ in the matrix of Zn. The nanoparticulates powders were characterized with an X-ray Diffractometer to determine the crystal information of the materials, a Scanning Electron Microscope/Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM/EDS), and solar simulator. The results revealed unique crystalline materials with optimal 2.45E-01Ω⁻¹m⁻¹ electrical conductivity.

Keywords: Smart coating, Modified, Structural properties, Corrosion and conductivity

INTRODUCTION

Titanium dioxide (Titania) is one of the most researched single crystalline metal oxide materials (Płacheta *et al.*, 2023; Daniyan, 2023; Diebold, 2003). One driving force for pursuing research on TiO₂ is the width of its applications (Diebold, 2003). Titanium dioxide is a preferred system for experimentalists because it is well-suitable for experimental techniques (Wang *et al.* 2006). Some of the inexhaustible applications of TiO₂ are found in; heterogeneous catalysts, corrosion protective coatings, optical coatings, varistors, photocatalysts and solar cells. TiO₂ is a semiconductor ceramic with electron-hole pair formed when irradiation with UV light from sunlight. This resulting charge carrier might transfer to the surface where they react with adsorbed water and oxygen to generate radical species. These attack any adsorbed organic molecule and can eventually result in total decomposition into H₂O and CO₂. The usefulness of this process varies from wastewater purification, disinfectant potential of the antibacterial properties of TiO₂, the application of self-cleaning type of coatings on windshields of cars and protective coatings property of marble for the preservation of ancient Greek statues from environmental attack (Carp *et al.*, 2004). The optoelectronic/electrical potentials of TiO₂ based nanocomposites have been reported by Popoola *et al.* (2017), Fayomi *et al.* (2018) and Daniyan *et al.* (2018). Liu *et al.* (2021) highlighted the unique properties which are usually exhibited by optoelectronic materials. These are considered exceptional candidates for the coming-generation of optoelectronic applications, typically because the materials display exceptional optical and electronic properties in different aspects. This work therefore presents the characterization of structure and optoelectronic properties of diverse titanium dioxide- based

nanocomposites coatings with a view to primarily develop a novel smart optoelectronic material for corrosion sensors in the oil and gas industries.

METHODS

Structural characterization

The phase and particle size analysis of the as-received nano powders were investigated with the aid of X-Ray diffractometer (XRD). The characteristic properties of the powders are presented in the Table 1.

Electronic and optical characterization

The electronic characterization was achieved in line with Daniyan (2023) and Daniyan *et al.* (2018) with the aid of Four-point probe electrical system attached with Source Keithley meter, that was interfaced with a Tracer software for Lab view. The I-V characteristic as well as

Measurement of the sheet resistance can be obtained using the following equations

$$R_s = \rho/t = (\pi t/\ln 2) V/I = 4.53(V/I) \text{ Ohm - Centimeter for } s \gg t \quad (1)$$

The electrical resistivity can also be calculated using the equation

$$\rho = t \times R_s \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the electrical conductivity can be given as

$$\sigma = \rho^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Multiplication of the resistance measured from the source meter and 4.53. We have the sheet resistance, measured in Ω/square.

(a) Electrical conductivity

Figure 1 presents the graph of the electrical conductivity of different nano-composites coatings using the equation 1-3 and in line with the sample deposition respectively. The conductivity value was very high for Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO-SnO₂ sample with 6.99E+04 Ω⁻¹cm⁻¹ in comparison to the other samples values' matrixes as shown in Table 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the XRD characterization, The X-Ray Rating of the XRD used was 40 kV, 30 mA and a Scan rate of 1.0 deg/min. The nanometer range of the powder precursors were confirmed from the XRD results.

Figure 1 presents the graphical relationship between the electrical conductivity of a range of nano-composites coatings with deposition trends on the samples. Sample Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO-SnO₂ displayed significantly conductivity of 6.99E+04 Ω⁻¹cm⁻¹ in comparison with others matrices' values as shown in Table 2. The cause for this enhancement might be traceable to improved steadiness of electrons' flow by the active nature of Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO-SnO₂ coating system.

The structural morphology of the nanoparticulate precursors is shown in Plate 1. The cluster of the nanoparticulates can easily be identified on the SEM micrographs. The Energy Dispersive Spectrometer confirmed the authenticity of the nanopowders precursors.

This heat treatment helps in the realization of improved crystallization (Fayomi *et al.*, 2018).

The Zn – coated surface that was thermally attacked could be traceable to the fact that the annealing heat treatment was carried out at 500°C which is significantly higher than 419.5°C (Zn melting point). It is remarkable that the homogenizing annealing effect of treatment led to grain refinement with better structure. Like metal matrix composites, the materials experienced internal stress build-up owing to many factors, and homogenizing annealing is usually used for stress relieving in materials. Furthermore, the annealing is one of the essential technological processes employed to relief stresses and mismatch reduction on films deposition (Daniyan, 2023).

For the optimal value of conductivity displayed by the Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO-SnO₂ sample, the cause for this enhancement might be traceable to better stability of photon current by the active component of Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO-SnO₂ coating species (Daniyan, 2023).

Table 1: XRD Result

Sample	Crystallite Size (nm)	Strain (%)
TiO2	15.9996	0.193
WO3	8.9.858	0.280
SnO2	14.019	0.16
ZnO	33.481	0.059

Figure 1: Electrical Conductivity of various Nano-composite Coatings

Table 2: Electrical/Electronic Properties of the Coated Nano-composite Coatings

Sample	V/I (Ω)	Rs (Ωcm)	t(cm)	ρ (Ωcm)	σ(Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
Zn-TiO ₂	8.24E+04	3.73E+05	6.00E+03	2.24E+03	4.47E+00
Zn-TiO ₂ -WO ₃	2.25E+04	1.02E+05	4.00E+03	4.08E+02	2.45E+01
Zn-TiO ₂ -ZnO	2.11E+02	9.56E+02	1.25E+02	1.20E+01	8.37E+02
Zn-TiO ₂ -SnO ₂	2.05E+05	4.52E+04	9.50E+03	4.29E+02	2.33E+01
Zn-TiO ₂ -WO ₃ -ZnO-SnO ₂	1.44E+02	3.18E+01	4.50E+03	1.43E-01	6.99E+04

The change in granularity on coatings surface of the nano-composite after subjected to an organized annealing is illustrated in Plate 2. From the obtained micrographs, it is obvious that subjecting the materials to this type of annealing heat treatment for 110 minutes at 500 °C temperature wholly recrystallizes the constituent grains.

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Plate 1: SEM Micrographs before Annealing at 500°C of the Nanoparticles (a) TiO₂ (b) WO₃ (c) ZnO and (d) SnO₂

Plate 2: OPM Micrographs after Systematic Annealing at 500°C of (a) Zn (b) Zn-TiO₂ (c) Zn-TiO₂-SnO₂ (d) Zn-TiO₂-WO₃ (e) Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO (f) Zn-TiO₂-WO₃-ZnO-SnO₂ (X 100) (Daniyan et al 2018)

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